

THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL MODEL OF ECONOMIC SOCIALIZATION OF THE PERSON

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Abstract: The article describes the views on the theoretical and practical model of economic socialization of children, teenagers and adolescents of preschool age, junior school age, based on the classification of life periods.

Keywords: socialization, junior school, adolescents, cultural-historical.

It is vitally important to educate the growing mature generation between transitional breaks with accurate knowledge to suit changing conditions. Based on this, one of the tasks before the experts in the field is to inculcate ideas about economic events during the formation of a child as a person, that is, to form knowledge about events and phenomena that appear in the economic world in accordance with the stages of childhood. At the first stage of socialization, the effectiveness depends more on the family, its socio-psychological environment and how the parents fulfill their educational duties, in particular on family socialization, in its later stages, the role of educational institutions and labor teams increases, and accordingly, socialization in a new direction - "**economic " socialization "** requires mastering *of children, adolescents and adolescents of preschool age, junior school age*, selected as the object of our research, as well as their activity, their position and attitude towards situations, events, objects and messages that are important to them - researching motivation and determining the role of the psychological mechanism that connects subjective reality with objectivity S. *Moskovichi* [3], J. Jodelet [4], A.I. Dontsov and T.P. Emelyanova [5], M.K. Block [6], M.I. It is carried out using the "**Concept of Social Imagination**" proposed by Volovikov [7]. "**Three-dimensional model**" of V. M. Karimova[8] is useful in determining that children's ideas about money are an important aspect of economic socialization . The reason: "Social imaginations are such dynamic structures that change during life, and the mechanisms of their formation and change are important in the processes from how the owner of imaginations perceives the social existence, to the processes of settling in the knowledge system of objects that have acquired personal meaning, manifesting in behavior, and becoming a personal experience. becomes important" [8]. From this point of view, this model allows us to measure the level of the imagination subject's knowledge about a certain "sociometric position" member in the family, his assessment, description and attitude towards money, which is directly reflected in his behavior.

Another methodological basis for our scientific research is L.S. It is considered the "**idea of the cultural-historical approach**" of Vy Gotsky [9] , and according to it, it is recognized that all the characteristics of a person are the active assimilation of one or another relationship and events in society by an individual. However, the individual does not simply accept the experience created by mankind, the achievements of culture, but also assimilates it with his own reserve and even innate characteristics. Such mastery requires from a person not blind imitation, but inner activity. For example, the pattern of economic behavior formed in an individual under the influence of microfactors [10] and the reciprocity of market relations established by members of society and the process of harmonization based on this [11] make it possible for us to determine the **level of economic socialization**.

Person who is the central issue of our research the process of **economic socialization** is interpreted as the result of his assimilation of existing traditional and modern values in society based on market relations. Economic socialization in this It is explained by the fact that the process has a social character, the understanding of the individual's identity, and is understood as a complex

combination of biological and social factors in human nature.

In this case, "**instrument → money → is purpose**" and "**cause → money is → effect**" the influence of the factor of group relations in its forms on the process of economic socialization of the individual and the socio-psychological characteristics of the system "social institutions → **life rules** → **attitude to money**" **in children V.S. The concept of "self-awareness"** proposed by Mukhina [12] and V.A., which explains the behavior of a person manifested in meeting needs and getting out of various social situations. It is studied from the point of view of Yadov's [13], [14] "**dispositional theory**". The basis of this concept and theory was the idea that the values of social importance are acquired by the individual through the existing norms and institutions in the society during human ontogenesis, and the realization of these values is realized through the process of self-realization.

Also, "activity → consciousness → personality" (A.N. Leontev [15]), "external ↔ internal activity" (S.L. Rubinstein) [16], "social environment and activity" (A.V. Petrovsky) [17], "self-perception and behavior" (V.A. Yadov) [14], "personality and social relations" (G.M. Andreeva and V.N. Myasishchev) [18], [19], "need and social satisfaction" (K.K. Platonov, V.S. Magun, M.Yu Semenov and E.G. Efremov) [20], [21], [22], "activity and personal development" (K.A. Abulkhanova-Slavskaya) [23], [24] Russian psychologists' "**theories of functional approach to personality**" with social content also serve as a unique methodological basis.

Theoretical and practical model of economic socialization of a person, which includes four stages of life cycles selected in accordance with the program of our scientific research (see diagram 1), shows us, the subject of economic relations, "sensitivity to economic events → priority social environment affecting the process of economic socialization of a person → effective result" is useful in explaining the structure of the view. In particular, in the process of economic socialization, the **preschool child's sensitivity** to the economic events around him is expressed through his independence in relation to hesitations about spending money. In this case, the most important social environment affecting the process is the **family** environment in which the child grows up. Also, this age period is called "**the stage of formation of economic literacy**" and the **effective result** of successful economic socialization in a child is: (a) the formation of a sense of self-control without damaging the pride of self-esteem; (b) able to direct his actions towards economic relations; (v) is explained by the fact that he was able to clearly define his goals as a consumer.

Although the next developmental stage of economic socialization of the individual in the model corresponds to the period of **junior school age**, sensitivity to realities, the child's voluntary internal desire to work subject to the will of adults and limiting his independence within economic relations, the full essence of this process is the child's appreciation of money. - is explained by the level of awareness of its value. The most important social environment influencing the success/failure of this process is the **reference group** (it can be a family or an educational institution). In particular, we call this stage "**the stage of formation of economic observation and consciousness**" according to the efficiency indicator. The effective **completion of the stage** is mainly based on the child's: (a) formation of skills and abilities to use money; (b) increased confidence in behavior due to awareness of the economic status of the adolescent's family; (v) is assessed by the extent to which he can demonstrate economic awareness as a consumer.

The third stage of the theoretical and practical model includes the **adolescent** period of personality development, and with the help of the social/economic roles performed by the adolescents within the framework of economic relations, the ability to think about or obey others, to protect personal/family property, and the well-being of their family is closely related to the country's economy. It is possible to assess their **sensitivity** to economic events by determining what they essentially understand.

Unlike the above age periods, at this stage the most important environment affecting the process of economic socialization of a person is the social environment in which their **peer** group operates. Based on our extensive theoretical and practical research, we call this period of development "**stage of formation of economic intelligence**".

An adolescent who is/is directed to enter into economic relations: (a) has a clear sense of

personal "I" while developing his/her identity; (b) having an independent opinion; (v) the ability to make economic judgments based on the value of goods; (g) indicates successful/unsuccessful socialization in the economic process, depending on whether or not he/she can show strong will to those around him/ **her** .

The last stage of our proposed model refers to the **adolescent** period of personality development. Adolescents, who are subjects of the process of economic socialization, by this age, by observing the socio-economic events happening around them, have the ability to express their personal attitudes towards them, and understand what can happen due to the struggle and conflict of interests, clearly demonstrate their **sensitivity to the events**. they do. In this, **microsociety** embodied as an impressive environment, basically, this situation indicates that labor groups are gradually gaining value in the life of an individual.

Without losing consistency, we call this stage " **the stage of economic responsibility and civility formation** " . The high-level option stage, in turn, has an effect on the process of economic socialization, and the **result of effective economic socialization in the adolescent** is: (a) being able to feel responsibility for the country's peace and development with a sense of loyalty; (b) feeling that he is contributing to the prosperity and well-being of his family by performing small household chores ; (v) to know that he has the qualities of preservation of natural resources and the environment, hard work, thrift, and generosity; (g) it is determined by the formed/unformed characteristics and skills to fully understand socio-economic problems, to be able to make the necessary decisions to solve them.

Therefore, the proposed model is far from amorphous, and in accordance with the future research plan, it is possible to create an invariant model that includes the next stages of continuous education.

In general, E.G. The theoretical and practical model of the economic socialization of a person based on the classification of Goziev [25], relying on their socio-psychological analysis, we put forward the following **practical recommendations** as a proposal:

1. successful economic socialization of preschool children, the educator of the preschool educational institution, in cooperation with the family members, instills in the children *qualities* such as: a) to have basic ideas about the national currency, b) to follow the parents' advice in meeting the demand for material needs ; a) to be able to direct their behavior towards economic relations, b) to establish the *ability to clearly define their goals as a consumer*, it is necessary to start practical work.

2. as a diagnostic tool in the activities of practicing psychologists engaged in organizing practical work aimed at increasing the role of "family-child-pedagogue" cooperation in the economic socialization of a person , working with students of *junior school age* , from the projective methodology "If I were a magician"; essay on the topic "The role of money in our lives " in working with *teenagers* , A. Fernam and M. Argyle's questionnaire "Determining a person's attitudes towards money " , from the methodology aimed at " Assessing the economic status of the subject "; in working with *adolescents* A.A. Kapustin and M. Yu. Semenov's "Unfinished Sentences", M.R. Rokich's "Value Orientation" methods, P.N. Ivanov, E.F. Kolobova's "Determining vital values of a person (Must-test)" projective methodology and V.M. Karimova, N.Sh. It is appropriate to use socio-psychological questionnaires compiled by Umarova.

3. In pre-school education, general secondary education, secondary special, vocational education and higher educational institutions, it is appropriate to use the process of the market economy and the psychological mechanisms that shape it in the gradual orientation of a person to economic relations. After all, strengthening the " family-child-pedagogue" cooperation is of great practical importance for the economic socialization of a person to take place in the appropriate direction and efficiently .

4. The school psychologist in cooperation with the teacher of economic sciences in the implementation of social projects aimed at the education of economy, entrepreneurial qualities in students of general education schools and the development of their economic consciousness, behavior and thinking on topics such as: "Teenagers and market economy", "Economic

socialization of a teenager in the context of family and educational institution" It is of particular importance that the group organizes roundtable discussions.

References:

1. Webley P. Ekonomicheskoe povedenie v techenie jizni // Ekonomicheskaya psikhologia v strukture jiznennyx reali. - Irkutsk: Izd-vo IGEA, 2001. - S. 87.
2. Mukhina V.S. Adult psychology. Development of phenomenology: uchebnik dlya stud. higher fly Zavedeniy / V.S. Mukhina. - 10-e izd., pererab. i dop. - M.: Izdatelsky center "Akademiya", 2006. - 608 p.
3. Hayitov O., Umarova N. Theoretical-practical foundations of development of the desire for professional growth in young people (on the example of family trees) //N Umarova-T.: "TURON-IQBOL. - 2001.
4. Mrs. Mohana Turaga / An Empirical Study on Impact of Internet Marketing on Buying Behavior of Consumers. NeuroQuantology | June 2022 | Volume 20 | Issue 6 | Page 8445-8454 | doi: 10.14704/nq.2022.20.6.NQ22834 .